

Factors Influencing Consumer Intentions to Adopt Digital Banking Integrating UTAUT2 and Security

Vanessa Surya
School of Information Systems
Bina Nusantara University
Jakarta, Indonesia
vanessa007@binus.ac.id

Joni Suhartono
School of Information Systems
Bina Nusantara University
Jakarta, Indonesia
jonis@binus.ac.id

Lusianah
School of Accounting
Bina Nusantara University
Jakarta, Indonesia
lusianah@binus.ac.id

Abstract— Digital banking provides efficient services but faces several risks, making perceived security and low cost affect the customer's adoption decisions. This study aims to determine the factors that influence digital banking adoption with the UTAUT2 framework extended with the variables of perceived security and financial cost. Using PLS-SEM analysis on 390 digital banking users in Indonesia, the results showed that habit, hedonic motivation, perceived security, financial cost, and performance expectation significantly influence adoption intention to use, while habit and behavioral intention influence usage behavior. However, facilitating conditions, effort expectancy, price value, and social influence didn't significantly affect intention, and facilitating conditions didn't affect usage behavior. This study improves the digital banking literature by integrating security and cost factors, suggesting that banks and fintech companies improve security and ensure cost transparency.

Keywords—digital banking adoption, customer intention, perceived security, perceived financial cost, UTAUT2.

I. INTRODUCTION

The technological advancement has a significant impact, especially on manufacturing and financial services [1]. As customer expectations change towards more practical and accessible solutions, banks and FinTech startups are innovating digital payment platforms to adapt to changing behavior patterns and remain competitive [2]. The focus of digital banking is more customer-centric, such as providing information about financial transactions without having to come to the bank. Five leading banks in Indonesia, Bank Rakyat Indonesia (BRI), Bank Central Asia (BCA), Bank Negara Indonesia (BNI), Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN), and Bank Mandiri (BMRI) have strengthened the value of transactions related to digital banking as a response to the rapid growth of the digital banking industry since 2021 [3]. Bank Indonesia reported a 30.50% YoY rise in digital banking transactions in July 2024, reaching 1.85 billion, it's showing that more people now rely on digital banking for everyday finance.

A survey showed that out of 339 bank customer respondents in Indonesia, almost 6 out of 10 were enthusiastic about digital banking services [4]. Based on survey by Finder.com, the number of digital bank users in Indonesia reached 47.7 million people in 2021, making Indonesia as the second largest country in the world in utilizing digital banks. In addition, McKinsey's report on Personal Financial Services in 2021, stated that 78% of customers in Indonesia actively utilize digital bank services in their daily activities.

However, in order to address issues like cyber-attacks, banks must enhance their services, particularly in the area of information system security, due to the increasing demand for secure, easy, fast transactions [5]. Digital banks, whose

services are all carried out in digital media, certainly have a tendency to cyber-attacks. A break-in case was carried out by a digital bank employee in Indonesia by successfully breaking into 112 accounts and stealing IDR 1.3 billion. Maintaining security in digital banks is essential to ensuring customers can rely on them to meet their financial needs [6].

In addition, the development of digital banks also provides several advantages for customers, such as easier information accessibility, reduced IT setup costs, and reduced transaction costs. However, there is still limited research conducted on the effect of financial or transaction costs incurred by customers on behavioral intentions to adopt fintech [7]. In order to address this gap, researchers utilize the UTAUT2 framework, to assess customers' interest in using new technology [8] along with significant variables like perceived financial cost and perceived security. The purpose of this study is to empirically address and resolve questions related to research : What are the factors that are influencing consumers' intentions to utilize digital banking, and how much do these intentions affect their actual usage patterns? Therefore, this study developed several research objectives : To identify and understand the behavioral factors, propose a model extending UTAUT2 with perceived security and perceived financial cost, also to examines the relationship between intention to use and usage behavior in digital banking.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Digital Bank

Digital banking is a form of transformation from traditional banks into digital service platforms, making it easier for customers to access traditional banking services such as account management, payments, transfers, requesting financial products, deposits, loan management, and other services [9]. Technology plays a major role in digital banking, including developments in financial services that leverage blockchain, APIs, AI, data analytics, mobile devices, payment methods, and other technologies, to meet customer needs [10]. Digital banking provides many benefits to banking organizations and customers. Digital banking minimizes operating expenses, saves time, enhances organizational monitoring, and improves risk management for banking organizations.

In addition, digital banks are also able to provide better quality products and services. Meanwhile, for customers, digital banks can simplify the transaction process and allow access without time limits even in rural areas [11]. Electronic banking services can be categorized into two types. The first type is traditional banks that provide their services with digital platforms such as internet banking or mobile banking. The second type is a digital bank where all services are conducted

online via the internet, allowing customers to do their banking transactions without having to come to a physical office [12].

B. Public Behavior in Using Digital Banking

Digital banking has changed the way society accesses and manages financial services, making it possible to do transactions via the internet rather than in person at branches. This digital transformation has attracted a wide range of age groups as it offers a more independent and flexible solution [12]. The increasing adoption of digital banking in society is also because of the convenience and quick service of digital banking [13]. In Sub-Saharan Africa, the access to mobile phones is driving the adoption of fintech services, which helps in developing financial inclusion [14]. In addition, the public now expects digital banking to be secure, transparent, and easy to access. With online comparisons, banks are pushed to innovate by offering exclusive digital services like mobile banking and improving customer interaction [15].

C. Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology 2 (UTAUT2)

UTAUT is a framework that can be used to understand and predict individual behavior towards technology adoption [8]. The four primary components of UTAUT are social influence, performance expectations, effort expectations, and facilitating conditions. UTAUT2 is the development of the UTAUT framework with several additional elements such as hedonic motivation, habit, and price value to overcome its limitations [8]. These additional factors offer more in-depth information about how users accept technology. UTAUT2 is frequently used by researchers to examine FinTech services, digital banking, and mobile apps [16]. UTAUT2 is used in this study to determine the primary factors towards the adoption of digital banking.

D. Research Method

1) Performance Expectancy (PE)

Performance expectancy measures how much customers believe that the use of technology can make their tasks more efficient and easier and also can improve their performance [17]. Digital banking customers expect that the system will efficiently and accurately handle their financial transactions, which encourages them to adopt and continue using these services. Intention to use the technology are positively correlated with performance expectancy in the adoption of numerous digital financial platforms [18] [19]. Consequently, the following hypothesis was established:

H1: Performance expectancy positively affects the intention to use digital banking.

2) Effort Expectancy (EE)

Effort Expectancy describes how a person feels at ease and comfortable using technology to assist them in completing their work. In this indicator, an individual will require less effort to implement and use the technology. On the contrary, if technology is difficult to understand and use, then people will have higher resistance and it will be difficult to adopt the technology. According to previous studies, a person's intention to accept technology is influenced by their expectations for effort [20] [21]. From this assumption, the following hypothesis was developed:

H2: Effort expectancy positively affects the intention to use digital banking.

3) Social Influence (SI)

Social influence is an indicator of the degree to which a person's decision to adopt a technology is influenced by the opinions of others and the social environment [8]. According to a study, people's decisions to adopt FinTech in Spain are significantly affected by the suggestions and opinions of their coworkers [17]. Thus, the following hypothesis has been tested out in this study:

H3: Social influence positively affects the intention to use digital banking.

4) Facilitating Conditions (FC)

Facilitating conditions is an indicator that measures people's perceptions of how well resources and technological infrastructure can assist the use of a system or technology [22]. Reliable internet, easy access to digital banking platforms, and other technical support may increase public confidence and encourage people to adopt digital banking services. This is consistent with previous research that describes how facilitating conditions affect usage behavior and intention to use [23] [24]. Thus, the following hypothesis has been tested out in this study:

H4a: Facilitating conditions positively affects the intention to use digital banking.

H4b: Facilitating conditions positively affects digital banking usage behavior.

5) Hedonic Motivation (HM)

Hedonic motivation is an indicator that measures how enjoyable or satisfying the user experience is in using a technology [8]. People will feel the need for excitement, happiness, and entertainment when using digital banking, which is what motivates them to do so. According to a study on mobile banking usage behavior by Baabdullah et al. [25], hedonic motivation significantly enhances actual customer usage. Previous research also states that hedonic motivation influences intention to use [23]. Therefore, this study proposes the following hypothesis:

H5: Hedonic motivation positively affects the intention to use digital banking.

6) Price Value (PV)

Price value is an analysis of consumers in their behavior to use technology, by comparing the benefits that will be obtained with the costs that must be incurred [26]. The definition of price value in this study is the benefits felt by users such as reduced costs when using financial digital banking services. Price value has been found to positively influence the intention to use technology in a number of studies [27]. Therefore, the following hypothesis is established in accordance with the findings from previous studies:

H6: Price value positively affects the intention to use digital banking.

7) Habit (HT)

Habit is the ability to perform a behavior automatically as a result of learning it [8]. Research indicates that habit has a strong positive impact on customers' tendency to utilize mobile banking [25]. A person is more likely to use digital banking services for transactions if they are familiar with digital systems. Habits have a big impact on how customers utilize products, according to earlier studies [23]. Therefore, the following hypothesis was developed:

H7a: Habit positively affects the intention to use digital banking.

H7b: Habit positively affects digital banking usage behavior.

8) Perceived Security (PS)

Perceived security is the steps it takes to protect data against security breaches during transmission on a mobile device [28]. One of the biggest barriers preventing customers from utilizing and accessing sensitive information online is considered to be security breaches or criminal activity. Furthermore, the degree of technology adoption is significantly impacted by security breaches in the mobile context [29]. Based on several studies, show that the security aspects of transaction or payment methods through mobile devices have a positive impact that encourages behavior to use digital banking services [30] [29]. Therefore, the following hypothesis was developed:

H8: Perceived security positively affects the intention to use digital banking.

9) Perceived Financial Cost (PFC)

Perceived Financial Cost measures the extent to which a person feels that using bank technology services will involve certain financial expenses [31]. The costs that will be incurred when using technology services are such as registration fees, devices, subscription fees, and transaction costs. As a result, if the cost of using bank technology services is still affordable, it will bring more users, but if the cost is too high, it will become a barrier for customers to use the service. Prior studies have demonstrated a positive association between the intention to adopt bank technological services and perceived financial costs [32] Thus, the following hypothesis has been tested out in this study:

H9: Perceived financial cost positively affects the intention to use digital banking.

10) Behavioral Intention (BI)

Behavioral intention refers to a person's readiness and desire to utilize a particular product or service like FinTech, while actual usage is the real action of implementing these intentions [33]. In digital banking, users will carry out their financial transaction activities according to their goals or behavioral intentions [3]. This is in accordance with other study showing usage behavior is positively impacted by behavioral intention [34]. Thus, the following hypothesis has been tested out in this study:

H10: Behavioral intention positively affects digital banking usage behavior.

This study's framework, which includes the UTAUT2 model and additional factor variables like perceived financial cost and perceived security, is as follows.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Measurement

This research uses descriptive quantitative methods, using quantitative data (statistics) to explain certain phenomena factually. In order to prevent bias in the sample process, this study uses random sampling, which gathers data from the Indonesian population that uses digital banking. The UTAUT2 framework is used in this study. The construct indicators in the framework, such as PE, EE, HM, PV [35], SI, FC, HT, dan BI are referred from Venkatesh et al. [8]. PS is adapted from Singh and Srivastava [36], PFC from Mensah and Khan [37], dan UB is obtained from Penney et al. [38].

B. Data Collection

Questionnaires were distributed to users of digital banking applications in order to gather primary data for this study. The number of question indicators is multiplied by 10 to determine the minimal research sample size [39]. Since there is no exact data on the population of digital banking users in Indonesia, we use this method to help ensure the sample represent the total population. As a result, this study needs a minimum sample size of 360 Indonesian digital bank users with 36 question indicators. This study uses a Google Form questionnaire with a Likert scale from 1 to 5 that is shared on social media platforms. Respondents applied a rating scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) [3].

C. Analysis Techniques

Because of the complexity of the model and the data's tendency to be non-normal, we use the PLS-SEM data analysis technique in the study [39]. SmartPLS 4.0 is used in this study to analyze numerical data on quantitative data and test statistical data through outer and inner model testing. The outer model consists of analyzing outer loading and then composite reliability to confirm reliability, then using convergent validity to assess validity, after that measuring discriminant validity. Moreover, in the inner model, we evaluate the coefficient of determination (r-square) and test the hypothesis. The analytical steps that have been described, produce outputs that are the main basis for the discussion of the results in this study.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This study collected responses from 400 respondents, and 390 of them fulfilled the requirements. Our respondents

consisted of 72.8% females and 27.3% males. Of the total respondents, 41.5% used Seabank, 25.5% Blu, 23.3% used Livin. About 42.3% of respondents have been using digital banking for 1-3 years, 41.5% of respondents have been using digital banking for more than 3 years, and 16.3% have been using digital banking for less than 1 year.

TABLE I. OUTER LOADING, COMPOSITE RELIABILITY, AND AVE

Indicators	Loading Factor	CR (rho_c)	AVE
PE1	0.736	0.851	0.588
PE2	0.780		
PE3	0.777		
PE4	0.775		
EE1	0.775	0.862	0.610
EE2	0.742		
EE3	0.767		
EE4	0.838		
SI1	0.832	0.860	0.672
SI2	0.879		
SI3	0.743		
FC1	0.832	0.850	0.654
FC2	0.791		
FC3	0.803		
HM1	0.859	0.851	0.657
HM2	0.737		
HM3	0.831		
PV1	0.862	0.899	0.748
PV2	0.880		
PV3	0.851		
HT1	0.793	0.855	0.596
HT2	0.679		
HT3	0.849		
HT4	0.759		
PS1	0.819	0.902	0.698
PS2	0.818		
PS3	0.829		
PS4	0.874		
PFC1	0.896	0.750	0.606
PFC2	0.640		
BI1	0.869	0.895	0.740
BI2	0.848		
BI3	0.864		
UB1	0.716	0.839	0.636
UB2	0.855		
UB3	0.815		

In Table I, shows the results of analysis in several research instruments. If the outer loading score > 0.7, it indicates a strong relationship in measuring latent constructs. Composite reliability expected to be greater than 0.7. The value of CR > 0.7, indicates the construct has good internal consistency. The AVE value must be higher than 0.50 to support convergent validity, the constructs in the model are considered valid.

Table II displays the results of the examination of discriminant validity. When each construct's square root of the AVE is greater than its association with other components, discriminant validity is confirmed. Every construct in this

study meets this requirement, proving that each one is unique and supporting the measurement model's validity.

TABLE II. DISCRIMINANT VALIDITY USING FORNELL-LARCKER CRITERION

	BI	EE	FC	HM	HT	PE	PFC	PS	PV	SI	UB
BI	0.860										
EE	0.465	0.781									
FC	0.568	0.600	0.809								
HM	0.639	0.519	0.611	0.811							
HT	0.719	0.469	0.558	0.546	0.772						
PE	0.516	0.607	0.507	0.543	0.531	0.767					
PFC	0.607	0.462	0.536	0.513	0.586	0.367	0.779				
PS	0.632	0.437	0.533	0.593	0.582	0.357	0.630	0.836			
PV	0.662	0.497	0.558	0.647	0.645	0.456	0.618	0.639	0.865		
SI	0.417	0.205	0.413	0.414	0.327	0.219	0.391	0.347	0.475	0.820	
UB	0.640	0.424	0.466	0.446	0.650	0.510	0.509	0.441	0.457	0.300	0.798

TABLE III. COEFFICIENT OF DETERMINATION

Construct	R-Square
Behavioral Intention	0.655
Usage Behavior	0.487

According to the r-square value in Table III, the independent variables account for 48.7% of the UB variation and 65.5% of the BI variance.

TABLE IV. HYPOTHESIS TEST RESULT

Hypothesis	Path	Std Dev	T-Statistics	P-Value	Result
H1	PE -> BI	0.054	1.979	0.048	Accepted
H2	EE -> BI	0.053	1.011	0.312	Rejected
H3	SI -> BI	0.039	1.808	0.071	Rejected
H4a	FC -> BI	0.059	0.555	0.579	Rejected
H4b	FC -> UB	0.059	1.170	0.242	Rejected
H5	HM -> BI	0.056	2.944	0.003	Accepted
H6	PV -> BI	0.062	1.624	0.104	Rejected
H7a	HT -> BI	0.058	5.947	0.000	Accepted
H7b	HT -> UB	0.065	5.706	0.000	Accepted
H8	PS -> BI	0.052	2.824	0.005	Accepted
H9	PFC -> BI	0.051	2.128	0.033	Accepted
H10	BI -> UB	0.066	5.076	0.000	Accepted

In Table IV, if the t-statistic is more than 1.96 and the p-value is less than 0.05, the hypothesis is accepted. Based on the results in table III, it shows that H1, H5, H7a, H7b, H8, H9, and H10 are accepted or these variables have a significant positive effect, then the rejected hypotheses are H2, H3, H4a, H4b, and H6.

PE has a relationship with the intention to use digital banks (H1). This shows that customers believe that using digital banking can complete transactions quickly and efficiently. This study's outcome is consistent with earlier research findings [17]–[19]. The intention to adopt digital banking correlates with HM (H5), this indicates that when

customers use a digital bank, they experience excitement or satisfaction, which influences their intention to keep using it. This result is consistent with earlier research [23]. Then, HT significantly influences both the intention to use (H7a) and actual usage (H7b) of digital banking. The more familiar users are, the more likely they are to adopt and consistently use digital banking. These findings align with previous study [23].

However, according to the study's analysis, the intention to use digital banking is significantly associated with PS (H8). This finding is consistent with earlier studies [29], [30]. Indicating that higher levels of safety and security will increase a customer's likelihood of using these services. Then, PFC has a positive association with customer intention to use digital banks (H9). This indicates that customers will tend to use digital banks if the costs incurred are affordable. This is consistent with earlier study [40]. The use of digital banking services is associated with BI (H10). This demonstrates that the higher a user's intention to use a digital bank, the more regularly they will use digital banking in their daily financial activities. Prior studies indicate that behavioral intentions influence how people use digital banking [34].

These significant findings support UTAUT2 framework, that individual factors and technology perceptions influence intention and usage behavior. The integration of PS and PFC strengthens the model by adding security and cost factors that are relevant in the context of digital banking.

Lastly, the findings from FC, EE, PV, and SI are surprising since they do not substantially predict the intention to use a digital bank. Users may believe that digital banking is already convenient (H2), making ease of use doesn't affect the intention to use digital bank [22]. SI (H3) doesn't significantly affect digital banking intention, aligning with earlier studies' findings [23], most likely because users are not influenced by others around them. The research findings show that PV (H6) doesn't affect customer intention to use digital banking, in line with previous research [35]. Since users already have the tools and features they need, FC (H4a, H4b) don't significantly impact their intention and usage behavior, supporting by previous research [10].

V. CONCLUSION

This study shows that factors such as HT, HM, PS, PFC, and PE motivate users to use digital banking in Indonesia. Habit has the most significant influence on behavioral intention. Therefore, it is necessary to create public policy such as digital financial literacy campaigns in schools or universities and reward programs to build digital habits. In addition, strengthening regulations on consumer protection and data security and privacy can support digital transformation in the financial sector. Additionally, usage behavior is strongly influenced by HT, suggesting that banks and fintech should promote consistent use until digital banking becomes natural. Furthermore, behavioral intention influences usage behavior, highlighting the need for strong marketing to help Indonesian banks attract and maintain users.

Then, this study found that FC, EE, SI, and PV do not significantly influence users' intention to use digital banking in Indonesia, this suggest that customers are more driven by habit and perceived benefits. The results of the study contributed significantly to the understanding of financial inclusion and digital transformation. PS and PFC have a significant effect on the intention to use digital banking, indicating that trust and affordability strongly influence digital

banking adoption. Enhancing security and lowering costs can drive financial inclusion and support national digital transformation by making more people feel safe and capable of using these services. On a global scale, these findings are useful for other developing countries promoting financial inclusion through technology. The model from Indonesia can be adapted to explore digital banking adoption in other countries.

VI. LIMITATION AND FURTHER STUDY

This study have several limitations, including the potential of self-report bias from respondents' subjective answers and sample bias due to dominance from certain groups. Other elements that have not been examined in this study, such trust or innovation in technology, may be significant determinants. These limitations have led to several recommendations for future study, first, the sample can be expanded to cover more diverse demographics or regions for broader insights. Then, variable of trust may be added to UTAUT2 model as a mediator between PS and BI, while innovation in technology can be included as an independent variable reflecting users' perceptions on technology advancement. Including these two variables helps the model better reflect the psychological and tech-based reasons people adopt digital banking.

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